

Pathways to smallholder resilience: A model of cocoa farmers' general resilience tested during the real-world shock of the COVID-19 pandemic

(to be included in the webapp platform) (MAX 6000 words)

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Abstract. Resilience concepts are often divided into general resilience capacities and specified resilience responses. We developed a model of general resilience capacities for smallholder cocoa farmers and validated it with data on actual impacts and countermeasures employed by the same farmers in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The general resilience assessment consists of a hierarchical multi-attribute decision-making model. We developed the model using a selection of indicators from an extensive sustainability data set collected just prior to the COVID-19 outbreak from 195 smallholder cocoa farms in Ecuador and developed a baseline evaluation of general resilience capacities. We collected data from the same cocoa farms on impacts and countermeasures implemented in response to the pandemic for the specified resilience assessment. By correlating general resilience performance with an analysis of the impact severity of the COVID-19 pandemic, we demonstrated a weak positive but not significant relationship between general and specified resilience.

1 Introduction

Changes in global food systems caused by disturbances like climate change, economic disparity, shifting consumption patterns, and political instability can create severe repercussions for involved actors. The global shock of the COVID-19 outbreak not only revealed the vulnerability of national and international health systems but further demonstrated how easily our globalised food systems and supply chains can be disrupted (Béné 2020). Farming systems, located at the upstream end of supply chains, frequently have to deal with multiple simultaneous shocks and changes while facing an increasingly uncertain future influenced by increasing market deregulation and price volatility (Darnhofer 2014). Export-oriented farming systems like cocoa farms located in low- and middle-income countries are particularly susceptible to unanticipated environmental or socio-economic shocks due to their dependence on other supply chain actors (Ansah et al. 2019).

The concept of resilience has been adopted in an attempt to better understand the susceptibility of farming systems to sudden shocks and disruptions (Folke et al. 2010). The term resilience emerged in the 1970s in systems ecology

research (Holling 1973). In systems ecology, resilience is described as the adaptive capacity of a system to maintain its functions when faced with unexpected disturbances (Holling 2001). However, the transfer of ideas from ecological resilience to farming system resilience should be viewed with caution as this implies that ecological and social systems operate more or less similarly (Darnhofer 2014). In contrast to ecological systems, farming systems are fundamentally agency-driven. The response to shocks and shaping of the system depends to a large extent on the perceptions of the farm manager about what is feasible and desirable and not on biophysical processes (Darnhofer 2021b). Furthermore, a focus on maintaining a system's existing functions may further entrench present inequalities, demonstrating the increased relevance of transformation in predominantly social systems like farms compared to ecological systems (Darnhofer 2021a).

Since its emergence from systems ecology, the concept of resilience has evolved considerably to be applied to a range of fields, leading to multiple definitions and operational approaches (Quinlan et al. 2016; Serfilippi and Ramnath 2018a; Tukamuhabwa et al. 2015; Meuwissen et al. 2019). Those concepts generally share a common goal of increasing the capacity to maintain the needs of actors affected by shocks while building the capital base (financial, manufactured, natural, social, human, etc.) required to provide livelihoods for the people who keep the system functioning (Cabell and Oelofse 2012). Through operationalisation of the resilience concept, it is expected that it may be possible to evaluate the management of a system, track thresholds that could convert into vulnerabilities, and maintain or guide a system towards a more sustainable system state (Quinlan et al. 2016).

This study aims to put indicator-based resilience frameworks to the test in a real-world setting, which is rare in the field of applied resilience research. We developed a general resilience model of smallholder cocoa farmers in Ecuador based on indicators for the three resilience capacities of absorption, adaptation, and transformation. The 170 indicators used for the model were collected just prior to the COVID-19 outbreak to establish a baseline resilience evaluation for 190 cocoa farms. Approximately 1.5 years after the COVID-19 outbreak, data on the actual impacts and their severity as well as countermeasures and their effectiveness were collected on the same cocoa farms. We hypothesised that cocoa farmers with higher general resilience ratings were less severely affected by the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and able to mobilise more effective countermeasures.

Resilience assessment

During the last decade, the academic literature has emphasised the relevance of resilience for agricultural systems and made substantial progress in approaches to measure resilience performance (Béné 2020). The apparent aim is to establish a concept of resilience for farming systems that allows for empirical assessments with comparable metrics and indicators (Kaldjob 2021).

Those resilience metrics potentially provide the means to evaluate a system's internal change, external change that results from interactions with institutional settings and disturbances, as well as change that results from unforeseen system dynamics (Quinlan et al. 2016). Especially when applied to farming systems, resilience has been embraced as a proxy for long-term sustainability (Serfilippi and Ramnath 2018b).

Following this approach, it seems necessary to consolidate a common understanding of resilience through its relation to the concepts of vulnerability and sustainability. In contrast to vulnerability, which is generally understood as a passive attribute of a system to cope with shocks, resilience is presented as the active response of an actor faced with a disturbance, based on the underlying capacities the system can mobilise (Béné et al. 2014). Sustainability can be conceptualised as the normative intersection between environmental, social, and economic consequences human activities imply but does not guarantee a successful response to a potentially unknown disturbance (Giddings et al. 2002). Thus, resilience could be considered a dynamic process lying between vulnerability and sustainability that can produce feedbacks (Ericksen et al. 2012) and is highly dependent on the agency of the affected system operators (Darnhofer 2014). Therefore, the resilience of farming systems would not be an end in itself but can be considered a means to reduce vulnerability and promote sustainability, complementary to the other two concepts (Serfilippi and Ramnath 2018b).

A characteristic of farm-level resilience that is widely agreed upon in the scientific debate is its understanding as the combination of the three response capacities absorption, adaption, and transformation (Cabell and Oelofse 2012; Darnhofer 2014, 2021b; Béné et al. 2014; Béné and Doyen 2018; Folke et al. 2010; Meuwissen et al. 2019). According to Darnhofer (2014), the absorptive capacity "denotes the ability to assimilate a perturbation without a change in structure or function", the adaptive capacity "is the ability of a system to adjust in the face of changing external drivers and internal processes", and the transformative capacity "relates to the ability to implement radical changes". These three components of resilience in the form of capacities can further be linked conceptually to increasing levels of intensity a shock is posing on a system (Béné et al. 2014).

Furthermore, efforts to develop a robust resilience framework often distinguish between general and specified resilience. The concept of general resilience, on the one hand, does not define the kind of shock a system will be facing but aims to describe the potential of a system to cope with uncertainty in all ways (Folke et al. 2010). It is assumed that general resilience at the farm level is based on the inputs to the resilience process in the form of capacities, and therefore only an estimation of the potential a system has to counter a broad range of shocks and disturbances (Meuwissen et al. 2019). The resilience capacities of absorption, adaptation, and transformation that compose the potential general resilience could be modelled as the different tangible or intangible resources a farm system has at its disposal when it is confronted with a shock (Béné 2020). Those tangible and intangible resources could be categorised as aspects of one or more of the five resilience attributes diversity,

modularity, openness, tightness of feedbacks, and system reserves (Meuwissen et al. 2019).

Specified resilience, on the other hand, describes the reaction or outcome a system is confronted with in response to a well-defined shock or disturbance (Béné 2020). It is therefore driven by the agency of the operator and more difficult to predict or measure than indicators for resilience capacities (Darnhofer 2014). A common pathway to assess specified resilience is to define resilience of what, to what, and for what purpose (Resilience Alliance 2010) before considering resilience capacities and attributes that may influence the outcome in response to the prior defined shock (Meuwissen et al. 2019).

Limitations of Resilience Assessment

Although there has been a lot of analytical effort to structure and confine resilience into measurable metrics, there are many barriers to applying resilience as a "label" a farming system can have or not (Darnhofer 2021a). In fact, measuring resilience so far is comparable to attempts of aiming at a moving target that gets constantly redefined (Darnhofer 2014; Béné et al. 2014). The object of investigation for resilience is a complex adaptive system that does not behave like a function of the sum of its parts but an intricate network of feedbacks that can change over time (Quinlan et al. 2016, p. 685). The nonlinear feedback mechanisms that characterise these complex systems are embedded into multiple spatial and temporal scales, leading to unpredictable dynamics (Darnhofer 2014).

A trend exists in managerial research to construct uncertainties as a risk where probabilities can be estimated or known, and future uncertain events are controllable (Scoones 2019). Even if identified parameters are well-studied, uncertainties always exist with unknown or unknowable probabilities that may result in misleading conclusions of risk-based approaches (Scoones and Stirling 2020). Indeed, this has been shown by many peer-reviewed studies that present similar parameters with several orders of magnitude differences, justifying a multitude of policy recommendations based on overlapping uncertainty ranges (Stirling 2008). That does not mean that risk-based approaches cannot be helpful when familiarity exists, yet a certain degree of humility is advised when dealing with the unknown (Stirling 2010), which is the case for resilience models and assessments.

Already in the 1920s, the economist Frank Knight (1921) stated that a measurable uncertainty or risk is so far from an unmeasurable that it is not an uncertainty at all. When uncertainty is at the heart of the object of investigation, postnormal science that engages with a broader peer community may be required (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1990). Other suitable methods may derive from postmodern science, like process-relational approaches, which aim to distance themselves from notions that objects of investigation, like resilience, in this case, are defined by an inherent property but rather see them as dynamic and in exchange with the outside world (Ritzer et al. 2001). This perspective

may be promising for studies on the resilience of farming systems that too often only focus on the predictable, thus negating the creativity that gets mobilised when faced with challenges (Darnhofer 2020).

2 Methods

Study region

Our case study comprises Ecuadorian cocoa farmers who are part of an in-house sustainability program and sell their produce through local intermediaries and a multinational trader to a Swiss chocolate producer. Due to the wide geographical distribution and high population of over 6000 farmers participating in the program, we selected eight supplier groups in the north-western part of Ecuador for the initial sample with a random subsample of 25 farmers per group (**Figure 1**). Fieldwork in Ecuador took place on two occasions: The first time was just before the COVID-19 outbreak in July-September 2019, when 190 farmers' sustainability performance was assessed in a comprehensive process (for more details, see Tennhardt et al. (2022)). The second round of data collection took place approximately 1.5 years after the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak, including 158 farmers from the first round of data collection, with the specific aim to evaluate the resilience of the previously assessed farming systems against the impacts of the pandemic.

Figure 1. Map of study sites in Ecuador (Manabí, Esmeraldas, Los Ríos, and Cotopaxi Provinces; Ecuador shown here without Galapagos) (farm sample $n = 190$). Illustration based on Open Street Map and geoBoundaries data, developed using Tmap and rgeoboundaries packages in RStudio. Source: Adapted from Tennhardt et al. (2022)

Impact of COVID-19 in the study region

Ecuador was hit by the COVID-19 pandemic while already struggling with a major political crisis caused by a government with low popularity, allegations of corruption, a weak political opposition, and a general social discontent (Garcia et al. 2020). This social discontent reached its peak with massive protests in 2019 against the drastic economic measures and cuts administered by the ex-president of Ecuador Lenin Moreno (Córdoba et al. 2021). The social and political tensions in Ecuador were further fueled by the concentration of capital in the urban centres, while the rural population remained widely marginalised as a consequence of the high dependence on the export of primary resources and extractivism that characterise the country (Carrión-Astudillo et al. 2021).

During the first months of the COVID-19 pandemic, Ecuador was hit much harder by the outbreak than reports from national institutions indicated (Cevallos-Valdiviezo et al. 2020). The death toll in the country during the first two months was actually 15 times higher than the official tally of coronavirus-related deaths, ranking Ecuador 1st worldwide in the number of deaths by million inhabitants during this period (Ortiz-Prado et al. 2021). Mortality rates were especially high among the most vulnerable groups with limited access to health services, dealing with poor working conditions, or generally suffering from poverty (Ortiz-Prado et al. 2021). The highest infection rates during the outbreak of the pandemic were observed in the coastal provinces of Guayas, Esmeraldas, and Manabí, which are generally more densely populated than the highlands (Fernández-Naranjo et al. 2021; Benítez et al. 2020), and where most of the farmers of our sample were located.

Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic reported in the literature that affected cocoa supply chains in Ecuador ranged from the loss of sales (Fountain and Huetz-Adams 2020; Teye and Nikoi 2021) to limited access to supplies and inputs (Mena-Coronel and Gutiérrez-Jaramillo 2021), lack of labour (Teye and Nikoi 2021), delays in transport (Kumar and Jolly 2021), loss of cocoa quality (Cadby 2021) and increasing inequalities in communities (Córdoba et al. 2021), among others.

General resilience evaluation

For the general resilience model, a hierarchical framework of 28 resilience criteria was adapted from Serfilippi and Ramnath (2018a). The framework was operationalised using 170 selected indicators (**Error! Reference source not found.**) from an extensive data set collected with the Sustainability Monitoring and Assessment Routine (SMART-Farm Tool) (Schader et al. 2016) just prior to the COVID-19 outbreak. The selection process of indicators from a total of 327 SMART-Farm Tool indicators was based on a literature review and group discussions. Additional relevant indicators were included and calculated from supplementary data and questions asked during the first survey. Indicators were categorised into criteria and sub-criteria based on their relevance for the

absorptive, adaptive, or transformative capacity of farming systems. The general resilience assessment was performed as follows:

First, all indicators were transformed in a way that higher values refer to better performances. Second, a separate Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was run on each sub-criteria category, and weights were calculated for each indicator based on the amount of variance explained by the indicator. These weights were then used for aggregating the individual indicators into the general resilience framework. The weights from the PCA results were used for aggregating indicators into sub-criteria. For each following aggregation step, we used the average value of the constituent sub-criteria. Each farm was evaluated using the final framework and given an overall general resilience score as well as scores for the different types of resilience capacities and criteria.

All statistical analyses in this study were carried out using RStudio desktop version 1.2.5001 (RStudio Team 2019). We used the R package "Utility" (Reichert et al. 2013) for the aggregation steps of the framework and evaluation of individual farms' general resilience scores.

Specified resilience evaluation

The questionnaire to evaluate specified resilience contained open-ended questions about the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and responses the interviewees engaged in to counter the consequences of the pandemic. The aim of the questionnaire was to get unbiased views from the interviewees without suggesting potential impacts or responses beforehand. Severity scores ranging from 1 to 5 were collected for each impact mentioned, and effectiveness scores in the same range were recorded for the countermeasures reported by the interviewees. This procedure allowed us to not only analyse the quantity of reported impacts and countermeasures but also to account for the quality of those observations.

Correlation of general and specified resilience evaluation

The output of the general resilience model for each farm was translated into a relative score of achieved resilience ranging from 0 to 1 for all criteria and capacities. For the specified resilience, each reported impact and countermeasure was weighted with the respective severity and effectiveness score and summed for each farm. The weighted sum of impacts was divided by the weighted sum of responses to create an impact versus response index. A higher value thus indicated a more severe negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (i.e. more severe impacts, less effective responses). The impact to response index was then correlated with the results from the general resilience model to identify relationships between both parameters. We tested for a significant correlation using Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient. A significant correlation would indicate that the general resilience framework held predictive value in determining outcomes from the COVID-19 pandemic.

3 Results

General resilience results

Figure 2. Graphical representation of general resilience

Specified resilience results

Farmers mentioned 24 distinct impacts when asked about how the COVID-19 pandemic influenced their lives as cocoa producers (Figure 3). The most commonly reported impacts were loss of sales (64.56%), difficulties with transportation of goods (43.67%), and reduction of in-country travelling (43.04%). The severity of most impacts was rated high, with most median values ranging between 4 and 5. The highest standard deviation for the severity of impacts was observed for cancellation of farmer meetings (2.00), followed by isolation at home (1.03) and increased cost of living (1.01).

Figure 3. Reported impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and their severity scores by farmers (n=158)

Farmers mentioned 21 distinct responses to the impacts the COVID-19 pandemic imposed on their lives as cocoa producers (**Figure 4**). The most commonly reported responses were the implementation of biosecurity measures (65.82%), reduction of travel to the market (50.63%), and consumption of traditional medicine (45.57%). The effectiveness of these responses was generally perceived as high, excluding acquisition of loans (mean = 3.40; SD = 1.67), staying informed through the media (mean = 3.50; SD = 0.71), reduction of workforce (mean = 3.75; SD = 1.17), and reduction of work on the cocoa plot, which has only been mentioned by one farmer with an effectiveness score of 1.

Figure 4. Reported responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and their effectiveness scores by farmers (n=158)

Relationship between general and specified resilience

Dividing weighted impacts by weighted responses shows a general trend that farmers who suffered more severe impacts also mobilised more effective responses (**Figure 5**). For the impact versus response index, an R-value of 0.34 and a p-value below 0.001 was observed.

Figure 5. Impacts weighted by severity versus responses weighted by effectiveness index. Shading represents 95% confidence intervals.

The correlation of general resilience scores with the impact to response ratio derived from the specified resilience answers displayed a weak negative relationship (Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, $r = 0.266$), indicating that more general resilience resulted in a lower impact to response ratio (**Figure 6**). The strongest relationship with the impact to response ratio was found for the absorption capacity ($r = 0.262$), followed by the transformation capacity ($r = 0.723$), and the adaptation capacity ($r = 0.723$). While all relationships were non-significant, rule of thumb values indicate an r value of >0.7 can be considered “strong” and analytically meaningful (Mukaka 2012). However, actual thresholds for meaningful correlation very much depends on the field of research and the expected magnitude of effect (Hemphill 2003).

Figure 6. General resilience ratings versus weighted impact to response ratio ($p=0.266$). Shading represents 95% confidence intervals.

4 Discussion

We assumed that Ecuadorian cocoa farmers with higher scores in our indicator-based general resilience model were less severely affected by the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and able to mobilise more effective responses. Our results show a weak yet non-significant relationship between general resilience scores and the weighted impact to response ratio. This was primarily driven by a strong correlation with the absorption capacity. This indicates that an overall general resilience score based on a combined values of the three sub-capacities is not particularly informative for an unforeseen shock such as the COVID-19 pandemic. A likely reason for this is the high level of aggregation of such models, leading to a loss of information for the specific and meaningful indicators that could assist in predicting vulnerability to specific disturbances. This generally speaks against overall measures of general resilience to uncertain and unforeseen event.

Disaggregating the results by capacity, we found the absorption capacity displayed the strongest relationship with the impact to response ratio. This makes sense, given the indicators composing this capacity relate to short term responses that aim to maintain the current system state. This capacity is therefore affected by the lowest level of uncertainty as it aims to buffer or assimilate disruptions without engaging in substantial changes in the farming

system (Darnhofer 2014). Thus, absorption may be a suitable target to evaluate with methodologies deriving from risk management (Meuwissen et al. 2022). However, short-term resilience could also negatively influence resilience in the long term (Cabell and Oelofse 2012), as farming systems focus on the predictable and may neglect the creativity needed to explore possibilities crucial for adaptation or transformation (Darnhofer 2020).

Our results for the adaptation and transformation capacity show only negligible relationships with the impact and response ratio. Although adaptability is often presented as the key capacity to evaluate the aggregate resilience of a system (Aboah et al. 2019), it already incorporates change, rendering approaches to assess standardised parameters problematic (Scoones 2019). Furthermore, actors usually adapt to a combination of different stressors or disruptions simultaneously, making disaggregation of adaptive responses rarely possible (Béné et al. 2014). Therefore, quantifying the adaptive resilience capacity in a flexible way that accounts for change and can be applied across a range of different systems is challenging (Quinlan et al. 2016). Especially as it is often not possible to define clear boundaries between adaptive or transformative change. Setting those boundaries would require knowledge about the moment when a system shifts from adaptation to a fundamentally different system state before the disturbance inducing the change happens (Darnhofer 2021a).

Standardised tools for resilience assessment seem to have limited potential to account for unpredictable dynamics that can translate into transformative change (Darnhofer 2021a). This limitation became evident during the selection of indicators for the transformative capacity, as we were only able to include indicators relating to the structural context a farming system is embedded in but could not account for drivers based on the agency of farm operators that may promote transformation. Similar limitations were encountered when selecting indicators for the absorption and adaptation capacity as it was often difficult to agree which indicators translated into short-term or medium-term resilience. Furthermore, the conceptualisation of general resilience as the capability of a system to cope with uncertainty in all ways (Folke et al. 2010) is often neglected when developing frameworks for evaluation. In the framework by Serfilippi and Ramnath (2018a), which we used as a baseline for developing our model, criteria like "Climate change mitigation" already imply a particular type of shock or disturbance. Rather than dealing with uncertainty in all ways, those kinds of frameworks provide a broad summary of already known risks that can be measured and translated into comparable matrices.

Limitations of the Study

The results of our study have to be interpreted with care due to the limitations we faced in the study design. In simple terms, unforeseen disturbances are by definition unforeseen, and the initial round of data collection did not have the specific aim of collecting indicators for a general resilience model. Due to the existing links between sustainability and resilience concepts (Serfilippi and Ramnath 2018b; Ericksen et al. 2012) and the extensive dataset of indicators

available for our sample (Tennhardt et al. 2022), we could make good connections between the frameworks, but the experimental design was improvised as a “natural experiment” following the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. As a results, we were not able to account for all criteria proposed in the general resilience framework that we based our model on (Serfilippi and Ramnath 2018a). Allocation of indicators to the resilience capacities of absorption, adaptation and transformation posed an additional challenge as it was difficult to set clear boundaries between them. As those capacities are supposed to be mobilised one after the other with increasing intensity of the disturbance (Béné et al. 2014), various indicators could have been assigned to more than one capacity, which was avoided to avert double counting. The study could have been improved using detailed analysis of individual resilience criteria and a more tailored indicator set. We are also investigating the sensitivity of the results to different weighting and aggregation functions, using expert-based weights and custom aggregation functions at each branch of the model hierarchy (Reichert et al. 2021).

5 Conclusion

Since the start COVID-19 pandemic, it has become evident that uncertainty and the unthinkable can become a reality at any moment (Darnhofer 2020). Risk-based approaches seem useful in dealing with potential events that are already known (Stirling 2010) but can be misleading when dealing with the unknown or unknowable (Scoones and Stirling 2020). Due to our limitations in dealing with uncertainty, resilience often defies measurement (Cabell and Oelofse 2012). Rather than conceptualising resilience as a defined property, it may be recommendable to shift away from simplistic understandings of resilience (Darnhofer 2021a). Shocks and disruptions have the potential to open up new possibilities for change and transformation (Darnhofer 2020). In practice, the ability of actors to engage in novel or culturally embedded solutions for unforeseen challenges may be far more relevant for resilience responses than quantifiable metrics that intend to apply risk-management strategies with unknown parameters. Thus, our results could not show a clear relationship between an indicator-based general resilience model supposed to quantify the preparedness of cocoa farmers to cope with unknown disturbances and the real-world impacts of an unforeseen shock in the form of the COVID-19 pandemic.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Capacity Resilience	Criteria	Sub-criteria	Descriptive Ind Name	Measurement Unit	Mean	Median	Min	Max
Absorption (Short-term)	Short-term Innovation	Adoption of Good Agricultural Practices	Number of elements in crop rotation	# crops in rotation	1.333	1	1	3
			Less use of synthetic chemical insecticides	%	0.727	1	0	1
			Less use of synthetic chemical fungicides	%	0.904	1	0	1
			Less use of synthetic chemical herbicides	%	0.439	0.3125	0	1
			Safe storage of hazardous substances	0=No, 1=Yes	0.832	1	0	1
			Protective gear for workers	0=No, 1=Yes	0.416	0	0	1
			Pruning of cocoa trees	0=Never, 1=More than never	0.921	1	0	1
			Checking cocoa plots for pests/disease or removal of infected pods/trees	0=No, 1=Yes	0.816	1	0	1
			Optimal harvesting methods	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.818	1	0	1
			Use of clean planting materials	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.306	0.5	0	1
			Optimal weed management	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.874	1	0	1
	Access to Information	Information on water availability	0=No, 1=Yes	0.100	0	0	1	
		Information on water quality	0=No, 1=Yes	0.037	0	0	1	

			Knowledge about risks of pesticides	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.167	0	0	1
			Awareness of potential safety hazards	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.363	0.5	0	1
			Training on the use of plant protection and animal treatment products	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.068	0	0	1
			Use of certified plant protection and animal treatment products	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.069	0	0	1
	Production System Robustness	Input Dependency	Total quantity of organic fertiliser inputs	kg/ha	3.916	0	0	135
			Total quantity of mineral fertiliser inputs	kg/ha	50.627	25	0	857.14286
			Number of active substances of pesticides used	# active substances	0.626	0.5	0	1
			Total quantity of pesticide inputs	kg/ha	1.923	1	0	38.75502
		Soil & Water Management	Agricultural area mulched	%	0.847	1	0	1
			Water consumption on farm	0= >100m3, 1= 0m3	0.745	0.75	0	1
			Management of riparian strips	0=No, 1=Yes	0.579	1	0	1
			Rain water harvesting from soil	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.000	0	0	0
			Water used for irrigation	0= >75m3, 1= 0m3	0.930	1	0	1
			Compost per ha fertilized area	dry matter/ha fertilized area	0.000	0	0	0.03
		Land Use Change	Area devoted to agroforestry systems	%	0.300	0.1628206	0	1

			Areas for promoting biodiversity	biodiversity area/total farm area	0.319	0.1239035	0	1.5
			Area devoted to woodland	%	0.044	0	0	0.5945946
	Economic Robustness	Diversification of Livelihood	Income from direct sales	%	0.030	0	0	0.75
			Extent of subsistence farming	%	0.359	0.3	0	1
			Products from agroforestry system	# products	1.374	1	0	6
			On-farm processing of products	%	0.182	0	0	1
			Variety of farm products sold	# products	3.247	3	1	8
			Dependency on revenue from main cocoa buyer	%	0.323	0.3338	0	1
			Dependency on revenue from cocoa	%	0.424	0.4395605	0	1
			Dependency on sales to main buyer	%	0.380	0.3801249	0	1
			Financial Assets	Low proportion of debt	%	0.908	1	0
		Liquidity of farm		0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.816	1	0	1
		Positive net income over past 5 years		0=No, 0.75=Yes, revenues covered all costs, 1=Yes, revenues covered all costs and surpassed them with a profit	0.308	0	0	1
		Relative yearly revenue		USD/year/ha	768.264	480.94118	15.746449	6700
		Insured against natural disasters		0=No, 1=Yes	0.011	0	0	1
			Insured against fire damage	0=No, 1=Yes	0.011	0	0	1

		Ownership of livestock	livestock units (LSU)	6.959	0.8615	0	114.918
	Labor Assets	No recent staff shortages	0=Yes, 1=No	0.826	1	0	1
		Farm manager workload	# hours	70.882	70	16	100
		Full-time job equivalents on farm	0= <0.01 FTE/ha, 1= >1 FTE/ha	0.507	0.5	0.25	1
		Household members working on farm	# HH members	1.084	1	0	6
		Short-term replacement of farm manager	0=No, 1=Yes	0.905	1	0	1
		Reducing physical workload through mechanisation	0=not reduced, 0.5=medium, 1=reduced to high extent	0.218	0	0	1
		Staff workload	# hours	57.503	60	10	60
	Physical Assets	Good condition of farm infrastructure	0=out of date & hardly functioning, 0.5=out of date but functioning, 1=good condition and up to date	0.661	0.5	0	1
		Water storage capacity	0=No, 1=Yes	0.000	0	0	0
		Good condition of storage facilities	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.561	0.5	0	1
		Availability of farm inputs	0=Yes, 1=No	0.905	1	0	1
		Age of cocoa trees	0=Yes, 1=No	0.812	1	0	1
		Diversity of crops	crop diversity	3.659	3.7127205	1	8.8252394
		Number of perennial crops	# perennial crops	0.170	0	0	1

Adaptation (Medium-term)	Medium-term Innovation	Adoption of Good Agricultural Practices	Use of hybrid cultivars	0=Yes, 0.5=Yes, but only when no other seeds or crops available, 1=No	0.468	0	0	1
			Low-energy irrigation technology or drip irrigation	0=No, 1=Yes	0.811	1	0	1
			Measures to enhance biodiversity promotion	0=No, 0.75=Yes, implementation within farm only, 1=Yes, implementation within and between farms	0.692	0.75	0	1
			Planned sustainability improvements	0=No, 0.5=Yes, but only few planned improvement measures, 1=Yes, several improvement measures	0.103	0	0	1
			Number of layers in agroforestry system	# layers	1.916	2	1	4
			Native tree species integrated within the agroforestry system	0=No, 1=Yes	0.337	0.25	0	1
			Beneficial organisms are protected and promoted	0=No, 0.5=Yes, untargeted measures, 1=Yes, targeted measures	0.100	0	0	1

			Cultivars chosen for resistance to harmful organisms and diseases	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.163	0	0	1
			Climate change adaptation measures	0=No, 1=Yes	0.037	0	0	1
			Commitment to principles of sustainability	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.208	0	0	1
			Not using seeds dressed with synthetic chemicals	0=Yes, 1=No	0.921	1	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered toxic to bees	0=highly toxic, 1=not toxic	0.485	0.5	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered toxic to aquatic organisms	0=highly toxic, 1=not toxic	0.269	0	0	1
		Access to Information	Informed about future market challenges	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.139	0	0	1
			Professional agricultural accounting procedure used for farm management	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.137	0	0	1
			Knowledge about potential impacts of climate change	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.261	0	0	1
			Informed about future policy/political challenges	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.100	0	0	1
	Production System Adaptability	Input Dependency	Soil analysis for determining nutrient contents and soil properties	0=Longer than 10 years, 1=Every year	0.000	0	0	0
			Mineral potassium fertiliser used in a needs-oriented way	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.000	0	0	0

			Relative expenditures for inputs	USD/year/ha	0.044	0.0136052	0.000481	1
			Inputs from contracted or stable long-term suppliers	%	0.657	1	0	1
			Proportion of inputs produced locally	%	0.390	0.4186046	0	1
			Externally sourced organic fertilisers	%	0.911	1	0	1
		Soil & Water Management	Crop residues not removed on agricultural areas	%	0.968	1	0.16	1
			Less soil compaction in agricultural areas	%	0.961	1	0	1
			Arable land devoted to legumes	%	0.207	0	0	1
			Perennial cropland devoted to legumes	%	0.002	0	0	0.2675676
			Measures to combat soil degradation	%	0.611	1	0	1
			Continuous green cover on land with high sloping gradients	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.707	1	0	1
			Measures to prevent erosion in low sloping gradient areas (excluding perennial crops)	0=No, 1=Yes	0.706	1	0	1
			Measures to prevent erosion in perennial crop areas with low sloping gradients	0=No, 1=Yes	0.757	1	0	1
			No tillage or reduced tillage	%	0.959	1	0	1

			Measures to prevent erosion in medium sloping gradient areas	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.719	1	0	1
			Perennial cropland with green cover throughout whole year	%	0.675	0.75	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered very persistent in water	0=Yes, 1=No	0.567	1	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered very persistent in soil	0=Yes, 1=No	0.602	1	0	1
		Land Use Change	Less deforestation over past 20 years	%	0.869	1	0	1
			Less conversion of permanent grassland	%	0.949	1	0	1

			Optimal land-clearing methods	0=On an area with native forests, established by slash and burn or removal of vegetation, 0.25=On an area with native forest, established by slash and mulch, 0.75=On a former plantation/fallow land, established by slash and burn or removal of vegetation, 1=On a former plantation/fallow land, established by slash and mulch	0.639	0.75	0	1
			Less degradation of agricultural areas over the last 20 years	%	0.987	1	0.2	1
			Formerly degraded lands regenerated over the past 20 years	%	0.877	1	0	1
	Economic Adaptability	Diversification of Livelihood	Long-term cooperation with other farms	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.211	0	0	1
Availability of alternative markets			0=No, 1=Yes	0.968	1	0	1	
Number of buyers (sales diversification)			0= 0 buyers, 1= 5 or more	0.577	0.5	0.25	1	
Off-farm income sources			0=No, 1=Yes	0.342	0	0	1	

			Sources of income other than farming	# sources of income	0.378	0	0	5	
			Cooperation between the farm and buyers (such as product development or advising)	0=No, 1=Yes	0.121	0	0	1	
		Financial Assets	Stability of profits over past 5 years	0=Decreasing, 0.75=Stable, 1=Increasing	0.480	0.75	0	1	
			No recent problems with lenders	0=Yes, 1=No	0.963	1	0	1	
			Investing in long-term improvements	0=No, 1=Yes	0.500	0.5	0	1	
			Access to formal or informal financial sources in times of need	0=No, 1=Yes	0.684	1	0	1	
			Longer relationships with customers	# years	8.043	6	1	40	
			Labor Assets	Succession on farm is secured	0=not clear, 0.5=relatively clear, 1=clear	0.761	1	0	1
				Minimal staff turnover	0= >60% of all permanent workers, 1= 20% or less	0.784	1	0	1
		Proportion of permanent employees		%	0.308	0	0	1	
		Household protected in case of farm owner death		0=No, 1=Yes	0.995	1	0	1	

			Job creation on farm	0=job cuts, 0.5=no job cuts, no new jobs, 1=new jobs created	0.558	0.5	0.5	1
			Compensation of overtime	0=No, 1=Yes	0.566	1	0	1
			Higher wages compared to local living wage	daily wage/living wage	0.276	0.2941176	0.1960784	0.4901961
			Equal pay on the farm	0=No, 1=Yes	0.791	1	0	1
			Commitment against discrimination	0=No, 1=Yes	0.430	0	0	1
			Measures to prevent discrimination	0=No, 1=Yes	0.000	0	0	0
			Support for disadvantaged groups	0=No, 1=Yes	0.447	0	0	1
		Physical Assets	Diversity of livestock structure	livestock structure diversity	1.206	1	0	3.8359857
			Land area of the farm	ha	11.543	7	1	102
			Diversity of crop types	crop type diversity	2.414	2.5764747	1	4.6537002
			Tree seedlings planted recently	# tree seedlings	196.759	0	0	2500
			Secure tenure rights over land	0=No, 1=Yes	0.905	1	0	1
			Stability of yields	0=Decreasing, 0.75=Stable, 1=Increasing	0.467	0.75	0	1

			Lower crop failures	0=The farm was affected by crop failures (> 20% of expected yields), 1=The farm was not affected by crop failures	0.900	1	0	1
Transformation (Long-term)	Social Infrastructure	Access to Education	Days of employee training	# days/FTE	3.031	1.329932	0	50
			Proportion of employees accessing training	%	0.012	0	0	0.6666667
			Minimal effects on children's school performance	0=Yes, 1=No	1.000	1	1	1
			Education of farm owner	# years education	7.463	6	0	16
			Education of household members	# HH members	0.621	0	0	4
			Sustainability training	0=No, 1=Yes	0.416	0	0	1
			Access to advisory services	0=No, 0.25=Yes, negative experience, 1=Yes, positive experience	0.522	1	0	1
		Social Security (Health & Wellbeing)	Social protection for workers	0=No, 1=Yes	0.516	1	0	1
			Workers have access to medical care	0=No, 1=Yes	1.000	1	1	1
			Workers have access to regular meals and toilets	0=No, 1=Yes	0.932	1	0	1
			Work-life balance of farm workers and manager	0=no days spent off work, 1= >15 days	0.267	0.25	0	1
			Farm offers workers meals or a kitchen	0=No, 1=Yes	0.900	1	0	1

			Protection against noise for workers	0=No, 1=Yes	0.553	1	0	1
			Household members have access to nutritious meals	0=No, 0.5=Partly, 1=Yes	0.968	1	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered to have adverse long-term effects on the users	0=Yes, 1=No	0.440	0	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered to be acutely toxic to the health of the users	0=highly toxic, 1=not toxic	0.343	0.25	0	1
			Not using pesticides considered to be acutely toxic when inhaled by the users	0=highly toxic, 1=not toxic	0.343	0.125	0	1
		Participation in Decision-making Structures	Employees free to join unions	0=No, 1=Yes	0.000	0	0	0
			Employees free to assemble and engage in bargaining	0=No, 1=Yes	0.000	0	0	0
			Farm supports improving sustainability regulations	0=No, 1=Yes	0.022	0	0	1
			Recognition of indigenous or traditional knowledge	0=Yes, 1=No	1.000	1	1	1
			Involvement in collective marketing with other farmers	% products sold with other farmers	0.017	0	0	1
			Involvement in environmental protection outside of the farm	# days spent on projects	0.649	0	0	20

			Involvement in social activities in the local community	# days spent on projects	3.099	0	0	52
			Farm supports health projects for the general public	0=No, 1=Yes	0.063	0	0	1
			Farm supports projects to enhance the food security of the local community	0=No, 1=Yes	0.147	0	0	1
			Female participation on the farm	0=male, 0.5=both, 1=female	0.382	0.25	0	1
			Fair resolution of conflicts with stakeholders	0=No, 1=Yes	0.895	1	0	1
			Mechanisms for preventing resource conflicts	0=No, 1=Yes	0.674	1	0	1
	Physical Infrastructure	Access to Water	No emission of pollutants into water bodies on farm	0=No, 1=Yes	0.660	1	0	1
			No conflicts over water quality	0=Yes, 1=No	0.974	1	0	1
			No conflicts over access to water or quantity used	0=Yes, 1=No	0.942	1	0	1
			Yields are not limited due to lack of water	0=Yes, 1=No	0.432	0	0	1
			Water from collected rainwater	%	0.006	0	0	0.5
			Water not used from non-renewable resources	0=Yes, 1=No	1.000	1	1	1

		Access to Energy	Electricity generated by farm's own renewable energy installations	%	0.947	1	0	1
			Electricity consumption on farm	kWh/ha/year	0.983	1	0	1
			Electricity derived from renewable resources	%	0.968	1	0	1
			Fuel derived from renewable resources	%	0.358	0	0	1
			Fuel for farm vehicles and machinery produced on the farm	%	0.000	0	0	0
			Heating energy provided by renewable energy or waste heat	%	1.000	1	1	1